

OpenMod Africa

Catalogue of models and their functionalities

DELIVERABLE NO. 4.1

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Table of contents

1	Introduction.....	13
2	Models.....	14
2.1	GENeSYS-MOD.....	14
2.1.1	Scope of GENeSYS-MOD.....	14
2.1.2	Detailed description of GENeSYS-MOD.....	14
2.1.3	GENeSYS-MOD Inputs and Outputs.....	15
2.1.4	GENeSYS-Mod additional documentation.....	16
2.1.5	GENeSYS-Mod references.....	16
2.2	OpenTEPES.....	18
2.2.1	Scope of OpenTEPES.....	18
2.2.2	Detailed description of OpenTEPES.....	18
2.2.3	OpenTEPES Inputs and Outputs.....	19
2.2.4	OpenTEPES additional documentation.....	20
2.2.5	OpenTEPES References.....	21
2.3	plan4res.....	22
2.3.1	Scope of plan4res.....	22
2.3.2	Detailed description of plan4res.....	22
2.3.3	plan4res Inputs and Outputs.....	24
2.3.4	plan4res additional documentation.....	25
2.3.5	plan4res references.....	25
2.4	InfraFair.....	26
2.4.1	Scope of InfraFair.....	26
2.4.2	Detailed description of InfraFair.....	26
2.4.3	InfraFair Inputs and Outputs.....	28
2.4.4	InfraFair additional documentation.....	28
2.4.5	InfraFair references.....	28
2.5	OnSSET.....	29
2.5.1	Scope of OnSSET.....	29
2.5.2	Detailed description of OnSSET.....	29
2.5.3	OnSSET Inputs and Outputs.....	30
2.5.4	OnSSET additional documentation.....	32

2.5.5	OnSSET references	32
2.6	EV-PV	33
2.6.1	Scope of EV-PV	33
2.6.2	Detailed description of EV-PV	33
2.6.3	EV-PV Inputs and Outputs	34
2.6.4	EV-PV references	35
2.7	Plexos	36
2.7.1	Scope of Plexos	36
2.7.2	Model Description	36
2.7.3	PLEXOS Input and Output Variables	36
2.7.4	PLEXOS case study – Ethiopia	37
2.7.5	PLEXOS references	37
2.8	SPLAT-Africa	37
2.8.1	Scope of SPLAT-Africa	37
2.8.2	Detailed description of SPLAT-Africa	38
2.8.3	SPLAT-Africa Inputs and Outputs	38
2.8.4	SPLAT-Africa references	38
2.9	Balmorel model	40
2.9.1	Scope of Balmorel	40
2.9.2	Detailed description of Balmorel	40
2.9.3	Balmorel Input and Output Variables	41
2.9.4	Balmorel application to EAPP	42
2.9.5	Balmorel references	42
2.10	Antares	43
2.10.1	Scope of Antares	43
2.10.2	Model description of Antares	43
2.10.3	Antares Inputs and Outputs	44
2.10.4	Antares references	44
2.11	PSS-E	45
2.11.1	Scope of PSS-E	45
2.11.2	Detailed description of PSS-E	45
2.11.3	PSS-E Inputs and Outputs	45
2.11.4	PSS-E References	46
3	Databases	47
3.1	World Databases	47

3.1.1	IRENA	47
3.1.2	AR6 Scenario Explorer and Database hosted by IIASA	47
3.1.3	Global solar and wind atlases	48
3.1.4	GridFinder database	48
3.1.5	Global Roads Inventory Project (GRIP)	48
3.1.6	COPERNICUS	48
3.2	West Africa Databases	49
3.2.1	Ecowrex Observatory for Renewable energy and Energy Efficiency	49
3.2.2	SIE-UEMOA	50
3.3	East Africa Databases	51
3.3.1	The African Energy Information System (AEIS):.....	51
3.3.2	The African Energy Commission (AFREC).....	51
3.3.3	East African Community Data Portal	52
3.3.4	EAPP.....	52
3.3.5	Other fragmented sources of data:	52

List of Abbreviations

AFREC	African Energy Commission
AFREP	African Renewable Energy Profiles
APM	Average Participation Method
CAPEX	CAPital Expenditure
CEM	Capacity Expansion Model
CLMS	Copernicus Land Monitoring System
CMP	african Continental power systems Master Plan
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DC	Direct Current
EAC	East African Community
EAPP	Eastern African Power Pool
ECOWAS	Economic Community Of Western African States
ECREEE	ECOWAS Centre for Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency
ESS	Energy Storage System
EU	European Union
EV	Electric Vehicle
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GIS	Geographic Information System
HV	High Voltage
IEA	International Energy Agency
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel for Climate Change
LCOE	Levelized Cost Of Electricity
MV	Medium Voltage
NECP	National Energy and Climate Plan
NTC	Net Transfer Capacity
OM4A	Open Modelling toolbox For Africa
OPEX	OPERating EXpenditure
POI	Point Of Interest
PTDF	Power Transfer Distribution Factor
PV	PhotoVoltaic
RE&EE	Renewable Energy & Energy Efficiency
RES	Renewable Energy System
SSV	Seasonal Storage Valuation
TSO	Transmission System Operator
UC	Unit Commitment
UMOA / WAMU	Union Monétaire Ouest Africaine / West African Monetary Union
WAPP	Western African Power Pool

List of Figures

Figure 1: Overview GENeSYS-MOD.....	15
Figure 2: GENeSYS-MOD Model structure.....	15
Figure 3: Stylised graph of GENeSYS-Mod Inputs and Outputs.....	16
Figure 4: Map of network and relative flows.....	20
Figure 5: Generation by technologies.....	20
Figure 6: plan4res modelling suite	24
Figure 7: Case example to illustrate application of proportionality in APM.....	27
Figure 8: Framework of the Open Source Spatial Electrification Toolkit (OnSSET). Adapted from: (Mentis et al., 2017).....	29
Figure 9: Daily charging demand map calculated for the city of Milano. The area selected for the study is shown in blue.....	34
Figure 10: Simplified schematic of the inputs and outputs of the EV-PV model.....	34
Figure 11: Plexos model design	37
Figure 12: Overview of the Antares model workflow (source: antares-simulator.org).....	44
Figure 13: Country profile data in Renewable energy sector	50

Executive Summary

This report is devoted to a description of models and databases which may be of interest in the scope of the Open energy Modelling 4 Africa (OM4A) Toolbox which will be developed in the OpenMod4Africa project. The OM4A toolbox is being implemented based on the Open Energy Models platform released in the open ENTRANCE project. It includes a database (based on the Scenario Explorer from IIASA), tools for processing and visualizing data, as well as linked models, to be chosen among those described in this document. The input data used for conducting case studies in OpenMod4Africa using the OM4A toolbox will be created based on available data in southern and western Africa.

This report describes first different models of interest and second available data sources.

The models which are described in this document are separated into different categories:

Models which will be used in OpenMod4Africa and are already linked to the toolbox:

- **GENeSYS-Mod:** The Global Energy System Model (GENeSYS-MOD) is a linear open source energy system model which is tailored to analyze long-term low-carbon energy transition pathways considering all energy sectors: electricity, buildings, industry, and transportation. First published by Löffler et al. (2017), it extends the Open Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS) framework and was expanded by numerous features and functionalities since then. Its main strength lies in the simultaneous optimization of capacity expansion, energy generation, and dispatch of all energy sectors, which leads to an endogenous optimization of electricity demand, taking into account the additional electricity demand from sector coupling by considering interactions between all energy sectors.
- **OpenTepes:** The OpenTEPES model is an open-source decision support system for defining the integrated generation, storage, and transmission expansion plan of a large-scale electric system at a tactical level¹. The user pre-defines the expansion candidates, so the model determines the optimal decisions among those specified by the user. Essentially, any technology can be considered by this tool, such as generation units (thermal -nuclear, gas, coal), energy storage (hydro, pumped-hydro, battery, electric vehicle, demand response, alkaline water electrolyzer, solar thermal) and variable renewable (onshore and offshore wind power, solar PV, run-of-the-river). Besides, the representation of the hydro system based on volume and water inflow data considers the water stream topology (hydro cascade basins).
- **plan4res:** plan4res is an open-source power system model, which includes capacity expansion (adaptation of the generation and storage mix as well as of the existing interconnections of a given year), optimization of the strategies for managing seasonal storages, and simulation of the system operation. Technologies: plan4res focuses on electricity. It includes all power generation technologies, electricity storage technologies, a representation of the interconnections between.
- Models which have been identified as necessary and whose linkage to the platform is being processed:
 - **InfraFair:** The (open-source) InfraFair model determines the network utilisation by agents (demand and generators using the network) and countries. Based on this utilisation and assuming that it reflects the economic benefits received by agents, it determines the responsibility of each agent in the construction of each element in the network. In order to reasonably reflect agent utilisation of infrastructure,

¹ Tactical planning is concerned with time horizons of 10-20 years

multiple representative snapshots of the annual network usage should be provided. InfraFair is a decision support tool for network cost allocation and tariff design for regional power transmission infrastructure, but it can be used for national infrastructure as well as other types of infrastructures operating on the same principle of flow (e.g. gas and hydrogen). Hence, the model includes all assets that have a flow usage such as power lines, transformers, breaks, series capacitors and phase shifting transformers.

- **ONSSET:** OnSSET is a Geographic Information Systems (GIS) based tool that enhances electrification planning and decision-making for the accomplishment of energy access goals in currently unserved areas. The OnSSET code base is open and modular and allows the users to specify spatial and temporal resolution of the analysis, GIS input data, technologies and costs. OnSSET is a bottom-up medium- to long-term optimization model that attempts to determine the least-expensive supply alternative to achieve universal electrification in each site by combining population settlements with various geographical features, socioeconomic data, and demographic information.
- **EV-PV:** The main goal of the open-source EV-PV model is to support planning and decision-making for the deployment of charging stations for electric vehicles (EVs). The EV-PV model is a set of geospatial data layers and calculation modules implemented in the open source *Citiwatts* platform (<https://citiwatts.net/>). This tool, developed as part of the ERANET OpenGIS4ET project, is a GIS (Geographic Information System) tool for territorial energy planning. It is based on the previously developed *Hotmaps* platform. Technological scope: for the time being, the EV-PV model focuses on passenger cars, as this is the main mode of road passenger transport in Europe.
- Models which are used in Western or Eastern Africa for conducting case studies in a close perimeter. Among those models, some are open and thus could be linked to the toolbox, if it appears that the former models are not sufficient, while others are not and won't be linked. Nevertheless it is important to be aware of what the later models may bring in order to cover all necessary characteristics of the OM4A models, if necessary by extending some of the open models.
 - **Plexos:** PLEXOS Integrated Energy Model is a simulation software designed for energy market analysis. It was first developed as an electricity market simulator. Its functionality was then extended so that the recent versions of PLEXOS integrate electric power, gas, heat and water. PLEXOS is a high-performance simulation platform, operationally used by energy market participants, system planners, investors, regulators, consultants and analysts worldwide. The PLEXOS simulations are based on mathematical programming. The system supports various planning horizons from long-term to short-term, and several different time steps: the simulated time frames can range from minutes and hours to tens of years. The PLEXOS models can capture specifics of short-term operational limits, as well as the effects of system expansion. Plexos is a commercial tool.
 - **Splat-Africa:** System Planning Test (SPLAT) Africa is a long-term capacity expansion model that includes the five SPLAT models of the African regions (North, East, West, South and Center). Most recently, the SPLAT-MESSAGE framework has been endorsed as the official planning tool for the development of the African Continental Power Systems Master Plan (CMP), an initiative led by the African Union Development Agency (AUDA) with the technical and financial support of the European Union (EU).
 - **Balmorel:** Balmorel is an open source economic and technical partial equilibrium model for analysing the electricity and combined heat and power sectors in an international perspective. It is highly versatile and may be applied for long range planning as well as shorter time operational analysis. It simulates the power system and least-cost dispatch, as well as optimizes investments in generation and dispatch. The model optimises production at the existing and planned production units and simultaneously simulates

least-costs investments in new generation and transmission, thereby finding the regional least-cost way to supply the needed electricity. The investment projects (as well as the year of investment, location and capacity) are chosen by the model via an impartial and objective least-cost optimization approach based on the input data provided.

- **Antares:** Antares-Simulator is an Open Source power system simulator meant to be used by anybody placing value in quantifying the adequacy or the economic performance of interconnected energy systems, at short or remote time horizons. With an adequate modelling of the energy consumption, generation and transportation, the software performs probabilistic simulations of the system throughout many year-long scenarios made of 8760 hourly time-frames each. The Antares-Simulator project was initiated by RTE (French Electricity Transmission system Operator) in 2007. The software is used to explore prospective visions of the energy sector, analyse the costs and benefits of a new generation or interconnection project, assess the impact of a given energy policy on the generation mix, or evaluate the level of security of supply of the upcoming years.
- **PSS-E:** PSS-E (Power System Simulator for Engineering) is an electrical system simulation software owned by Siemens. It is used for static studies (distribution of power flows, network losses, calculation of short-circuit currents) and also for dynamic studies (simulate the behavior of an electrical system following one or more events, like the connection or disconnection of a structure, the triggering of a production group, the appearance and disappearance of a short circuit, a variation in voltage or power setpoint for a group, etc.). PSS-E is a commercial tool.

The following data sources will be investigated:

■ **World Databases:**

- **IRENA statistics**

IRENA publishes detailed statistics on renewable energy capacity, power generation and renewable energy balances. This data is collected directly from members using the IRENA Renewable Energy Statistics questionnaire and is also supplemented by desk research where official statistics are not available. Renewable power-generation capacity statistics are released annually in March. Additionally, renewable power generation and renewable energy balances datasets are released in July.

- **IRENA Model Supply Regions (MSRs)**

This database contains model-ready, technology-based datasets for the potential of solar and on-shore wind across the African countries. Each input technology includes energy information (capacity factor and energy potential), cost characteristics (levelized cost) as well as locational coordinates. The database can be downloaded in a form of a shape file and excel/csv files.

- **AR6 Scenario Explorer and Database hosted by IIASA**

This database (hosted in a IIASA Scenario Explorer) presents an ensemble of quantitative, model-based pathways underpinning the Sixth Assessment Report (AR6) of Working Group III by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), entitled *Climate Change 2022: Mitigation of Climate Change*

- **Global solar and wind atlases**

The database include the primary potential of solar and wind energy (in terms of irradiance and wind speed) across the entire world. The database can be downloaded in a form of a raster and it can be selected for a specific region or country.

- **GridFinder database**

The database includes the existing transmission and distribution networks of all countries in the world (each with voltage and locational information). The database is based on opensource information and can be downloaded in the form of shape files or image (.tif) files for any region or country.

- ***Global Roads Inventory Project (GRIP)***

The database includes information about existing and future roads around the world. It consists of global and regional vector datasets in ESRI file geodatabase and shapefile format and global raster datasets of road density at a 5 arcminutes resolution (~8x8km).

- ***COPERNICUS Land Monitoring Service***

The Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (CLMS) provides geospatial information on land cover and its changes, land use, vegetation state, water cycle and Earth's surface energy variables to a broad range of users in Europe and across the World in the field of environmental terrestrial applications.

- **West Africa Databases**

- ***Ecowrex Observatory for Renewable energy and Energy Efficiency***

ECOWREX is a web platform providing reliable data and information on energy resources, infrastructure and potential policy resources at regional and national level to help policy makers, project developers and investors as well as other stakeholders for evidence-based decision making and planning.

- ***SIE-UEMOA***

UEMOA is an extension of the West African Monetary Union (UMOA). The SIE-UEMOA database includes detailed energy balances, energy indicators (sectoral and energy policy monitoring), environmental and climatic indicators, results of prospective analysis of energy demand, and energy statistics from 2010 to 2020 for Benin, Burkina Faso, Côte d'Ivoire, Guinea-Bissau, Mali, Niger, Senegal and Togo.

- **East Africa Databases**

- ***The African Energy Information System (AEIS):***

AEIS is a decision-making tool which is comprised of a continental energy database and other energy information and data visualisation tools. The AEIS was created by AFREC (AFRICAN Energy Commission) in 2012 to coordinate Africa's energy data collection, validation and dissemination at national, regional and continental level. It includes data such as energy, production and imports per fuel, biomass potential and hydro power plants.

- ***The African Energy Commission (AFREC)***

The African Energy Commission (AFREC) is an organ of the African Union in charge of ensuring, coordinating and harmonizing development and integration of energy resources on the African continent. This database includes among others data related to economy, energy and land use.

- ***East African Community Data Portal***

The East African Community Data Portal is a common workplace that allows data users to easily explore, visualize and download large datasets. This repository will provide a one-stop interface to access EAC statistical data in the following Sectors: External Sector, Government Finance, Consumer Price Index, Monetary and Finance, National Accounts, Agriculture Food and Nutrition, Poverty and Migration Statistics.

1 Introduction

The Horizon Europe Energy project 101118123 – OpenMod4Africa (Open Modelling Toolbox for development of long-term pathways for the energy system in Africa) is a three-year project (2023–2026) about development of an energy modelling toolbox for analyses of the future energy and power systems in Africa. Furthermore, capacity building among African experts in use and development of the toolbox is a core element in the project.

The main objective is to contribute to an improved and robust understanding of how to develop an energy and a power supply to all Africans by making available, demonstrating and using an open modelling Toolbox. The Toolbox will be populated with a suite of open integrated state-of-the-art models and a common database including all necessary data for conducting among other scenario building exercises at regional, national and pan-African level. Two case studies are demonstrating the use of the Toolbox, and in addition providing new insight into important challenges related to the energy transition. The research in the project is done in dialogue with two stakeholder groups, one in the Eastern African Power Pool region and one in the Western African Power Pool region.

The objectives of WP4 ,Open Modelling for Africa Toolbox (OM4A) are the following:

1. Based on The Open Platform from the H2020 project Open ENTRANCE, develop the OM4A Toolbox as collection of integrated and fully open state-of-the-art tools and a database for storing and exchanging data.
2. Develop a catalogue of models mapped with modelling needs.
3. Develop tools for presentation of assumptions and results of pathways for development of secure, sustainable and cost-efficient energy systems in regions in Africa.
4. Develop materials for training African scientific experts in using the Toolbox for exploring pathways for energy systems.
5. Train one African scientific partner in maintaining the database.

This deliverable aims at completing Objective 2, via Task 4.1 ‘Assessment of existing models and databases’.

It is composed of 2 chapters, dedicated to models and databases.

In chapter 2 ‘Models’, we describe the models already linked to the platform (GENeSYS-MOD, openTEPES and plan4res), as well as the models InfraFair, ONsSET and EV-PV, whose linkage is currently being performed. It also includes other models which are currently used in West or East Africa (Plexos, Balmorel, PSS-E), as well as another related well-known model (Antares). It includes one section per model, organised as follows:

- Scope of model: short description of the model, technologies involved, geographic and time horizon and granularities.
- Detailed model description
- Inputs and Outputs
- References

Chapter 3 ‘Databases’, is organised with a geographic point of view. It includes first a section dedicated to world wide databases, then a section dedicated to Africa wide databases and finally 2 sections dedicated to Western Africa databases and Eastern Africa databases.

2 Models

2.1 GENeSYS-MOD

2.1.1 Scope of GENeSYS-MOD

The Global Energy System Model (GENeSYS-MOD) is a linear open source energy system model which is tailored to analyze long-term low-carbon energy transition pathways considering all energy sectors: electricity, buildings, industry, and transportation. First published by Löffler et al. (2017), it extends the Open Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS) framework and was expanded by numerous features and functionalities since then. Its main strength lies in the simultaneous optimization of capacity expansion, energy generation, and dispatch of all energy sectors, which leads to an endogenous optimization of electricity demand, taking into account the additional electricity demand from sector coupling by considering interactions between all energy sectors.

2.1.2 Detailed description of GENeSYS-MOD

GENeSYS-MOD optimises the long-term development of the energy system, with a detailed approach to coupling of the electricity, heat, and transportation sectors. It takes as an input the energy demands per uses in different sectors: heating, mobility, power. Other than for heating or transport-, the available technologies and primary energies (fossil fuels, gases, but also renewables) with their potentials and costs, it computes the optimum pathways in terms of energy mix, including generation, transformation and storage. It can be constrained by a limit in term of volume of emissions or account for CO₂ prices. It is mainly used to develop energy system scenarios computing the necessary capacities to meet these demands. It has been used in numerous studies and projects (e.g. Germany (Bartholdsen et al., 2019), Europe (Hainsch et al., 2021), South Africa (Hanto et al., 2021) or Japan (Burandt, 2021)).

In essence, GENeSYS-MOD can be illustrated as a flow-based cost-optimization model. The different nodes are represented as Technologies, which are connected by Fuels. Examples for Technologies are production entities like wind or solar power, conversion technologies like heat pumps, storages, or vehicles. Fuels serve as connections between these technologies and can be interpreted as the arcs of the network. In general, Fuels represent energy carriers like electricity or fossil fuels, but also more abstract units like demands of a specific energy carrier or areas of land are classified as Fuels. Also, Technologies might require multiple different Fuels or can have more than one output fuel. As an example, a combined heat and power plant could use coal as an input fuel and produce electricity and heating energy as an output fuel. Efficiencies of the technologies are being accounted for in this exact process, which would allow to model energy losses due to conversion. Energy demands are classified into three main categories: electricity, heating, and transportation. They are exogenously defined for every region and each year. The model then seeks to meet these demands through a combination of Technologies and trade between the different regions.

The main limitations are the size of the optimisation problem and the available computing power, which affect the time it takes for the model to find an optimal solution. While a high level of detail is achieved in sector coupling, there is usually a trade-off as this leads to a reduction in spatial and temporal resolution.

Figure 1 gives a general overview of the different *Technologies* and the connections between them:

Figure 1: Overview GENeSYS-MOD

The GENeSYS-MOD framework consists of multiple blocks of functionality, that ultimately originate from the OSeMOSYS framework. Figure 2 shows the underlying block structure, with the additions made in the current model version (example of changes: the option to compute variable years instead of the fixed 5-year periods, a district heating module, the inclusion of axis-tracking PV...).

Figure 2: GENeSYS-MOD Model structure

2.1.3 GENeSYS-MOD Inputs and Outputs

Inputs and outputs in GENeSYS-MOD are in either in csv (Comma Separated Values) or excel format. Figure 3 illustrates a simplified version of model inputs, components, and outputs.

Figure 3: Stylised graph of GENeSYS-Mod Inputs and Outputs

Main Inputs:

- Baseline demand data (final energy per uses)
- Renewable potential
- Cost assumptions (investment and operation costs per technology)
- Weather data
- Installed capacities and grid at the starting year
- Political targets (carbon price and/or emissions)

Main Outputs:

- Primary energy demand (per fuel)
- Sectoral demands
- Technology investments
- Costs
- Renewable generation
- Fossil fuel phase-outs
- CO2 emissions

Due to the large amount of data inputs and outputs, readers are referred to [technical documentation \(here\)](#)

2.1.4 GENeSYS-Mod additional documentation

- Mathematical formulation:
 - [Löffler, K., Hainsch, K., Burandt, T., Oei, P.Y., Kemfert, C., Von Hirschhausen, C., 2017. Designing a Model for the Global Energy System—GENeSYS-MOD: An Application of the Open-Source Energy Modeling System \(OSeMOSYS\). Energies 10, 1468. URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/10/10/1468>.](#)
- Documentation, quick-start guide, and a sample dataset
 - <https://git.tu-berlin.de/genesysmod/genesys-mod-public>.

2.1.5 GENeSYS-Mod references

- [1] Bartholdsen, H.-K., Eidens, A., Löffler, K., Seehaus, F., Wejda, F., Burandt, T., Oei, P.- Y., Kemfert, C., von Hirschhausen, C., 2019. Pathways for Germany’s low-carbon energy transformation towards 2050. Energies 12 (15), 2988. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/en12152988> , URL <https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/12/15/2988>
- [2] Burandt, T., 2021. Analyzing the necessity of hydrogen imports for net-zero emission scenarios in Japan. Appl. Energy 298, 117265. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2021.117265>

- [3] Hainsch, K., Burandt, T., Löffler, K., Kemfert, C., Oei, P.-Y., von Hirschhausen, C., 2021. Emission pathways towards a low-carbon energy system for Europe: A modelbased analysis of decarbonization scenarios. *Energy J.* 42 (01), <http://dx.doi.org/10.5547/01956574.42.5.khai>, URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306261921006814?via%3Dihub>.
- [4] Hanto, J., Krawielicki, L., Krumm, A., Moskalenko, N., Löffler, K., Hauenstein, C., Oei, P.-Y., 2021. Effects of decarbonization on the energy system and related employment effects in South Africa. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 124, 73–84. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2021.06.001>, URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1462901121001532>.
- [5] Löffler, K., Hainsch, K., Burandt, T., Oei, P.Y., Kemfert, C., Von Hirschhausen, C., 2017. Designing a Model for the Global Energy System—GENeSYS-MOD: An Application of the Open-Source Energy Modeling System (OSeMOSYS). *Energies* 10, 1468. URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/10/10/1468>.
- [6] Candas, S., Muschner, C., Buchholz S., Bramstoft, R., van Ouwerkerk, J., Hainsch, K., Löffler, K., Günther, S., Berendes, S., Nguyen, S., Justin, A., 2022, Code exposed: Review of five open-source frameworks for modeling renewable energy systems. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, Volume 161, 112272, ISSN 1364-0321, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2022.112272>

2.2 OpenTEPES

2.2.1 Scope of OpenTEPES

The OpenTEPES model is a decision support system for defining the integrated generation, storage, and transmission expansion plan of a large-scale electric system at a tactical level². The user pre-defines the expansion candidates, so the model determines the optimal decisions among those specified by the user. Essentially, any technology can be considered by this tool, such as generation units (thermal -nuclear, gas, coal), energy storage (hydro, pumped-hydro, battery, electric vehicle, demand response, alkaline water electrolyzer, solar thermal) and variable renewable (onshore and offshore wind power, solar PV, run-of-the-river). Besides, the representation of the hydro system based on volume and water inflow data considers the water stream topology (hydro cascade basins).

The time scope of the model can range from one up to several years with an hourly (bi-hourly, tri-hourly) time step. The time division allows the user to consider a user-defined flexible representation of the periods for evaluating the system operation. Moreover, it can be run with chronological periods of several consecutive hours (bi-hourly, tri-hourly resolution) to decrease the computational burden without losing accuracy. The model can be run considering a single expansion planning stage (year) or multiple stages (years) to allow the analysis of the system evolution. The time definition can also be used to specify non chronological representative periods (e.g., days, weeks) to evaluate the system operation.

Geographically, the model defines nodes, zones, areas (e.g., countries), and regions (e.g., continental southwest Europe).

The main model limitation is the maximum size of the optimization problem to be solved and, consequently, the solution time. For example, a European operation case study with hourly timestep can be formulated into a 22 million constraints and 27 million variables linear problem. The mainland Spain operation case includes 5 million constraints and 5 million variables (1.3 million being binary).

OpenTEPES has been used in several European and Spanish research projects to analyze the electricity sector in Europe or in Spain. Some of the projects have analyzed the trade-off between electricity network and storage systems as possible ways to contribute to the decarbonization. In Spain, it has been used by the **Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge (MITECO)** [National Energy and Climate Plan \(NECP\) 2023-2030](#) in June 2023. It is integrated into the [open energy system modelling platform](#), helping model Europe's energy system.

2.2.2 Detailed description of OpenTEPES

The objective function incorporates the two main quantifiable costs:

- CAPEX (ie. CAPital EXpenditure) cost of investments in generation, storage, and transmission
- OPEX (OPerating expenditure): expected variable operation costs (including generation, consumption, emission, and reliability costs).

The model formulates a two-stage stochastic optimization problem, including generation, storage, and electric and hydrogen network binary investment/retirement decisions, generation operation decisions (commitment, startup, and shutdown decisions are also binary), and electric line-switching decisions. The capacity expansion considers adequacy system reserve margin constraints.

² Tactical planning is concerned with time horizons of 10-20 years

The operation model is an electric network-constrained unit commitment one based on a tight and compact formulation, including operating reserves with a direct current power flow, including electric line switching decisions. Electric network ohmic losses are considered proportional to the electric line flow. It considers different energy storage systems, e.g., pumped-hydro storage, battery, demand response, electric vehicles, solar thermal, alkaline water electrolyzer, etc. It allows analyzing the trade-off between the investment in generation/transmission and the investment or use of storage capacity. The model allows also the user to consider a representation of the hydro system based on volume and water inflow data considering the water stream topology (hydro cascade basins). If these data are not available, the model can run considering an energy-based representation of the hydro system. OpenTEPES also includes the representation of the coverage of hydrogen demand with the production of hydrogen by electrolyzers (consumption of electricity to produce hydrogen) and a hydrogen network to distribute the hydrogen produced. If these systems are not available, the model is run just for the electric system.

2.2.3 OpenTEPES Inputs and Outputs

Input data are introduced in CSV files. Output results are provided in CSV files and graphical plots.

All the input files required are specified at <https://opentepes.readthedocs.io/en/latest/InputData.html>. Essentially, these are 1) dictionary files to define all the possible elements of the corresponding sets of the optimization problem, and 2) data files where the quantitative system information is introduced.

Main Inputs:

- **Electricity demand:** hourly electricity demand or hourly profiles and annual electricity demand
- **Interconnections:** characteristics of (existing) transmission lines between regions (capacity, capital cost, reactance and loss factor)
- Generation technologies:
 - **Thermal generation:** capacity, variable cost, dynamic constraints for each individual plant
 - **Hydro power** (separated into hydro with reservoir, pumped storage and run of river): capacity, efficiency of pumping, volume, inflows, variable cost, seasonality (daily, weekly, monthly, etc)
 - **Wind Power and Solar PV** (PhotoVoltaic): capacity, variable cost and hourly profiles

Main Outputs:

- **Investment:** generation, storage, hydro reservoirs, electric lines and hydrogen pipelines) investment decisions and cost
- **Operation:** unit commitment, startup, and shutdown of non-renewable units, unit output and aggregation by technologies (thermal, storage hydro, pumped-hydro storage, RES -Renewable energy Sources-), RES curtailment, electric line and hydrogen pipeline flows, line ohmic losses, node voltage angles, upward and downward operating reserves, ESS (Energy Storage System) inventory levels, hydro reservoir volumes, power and hydrogen not served
- **Emissions:** CO2 emissions by unit
- **Marginal values:** locational Short-Run Marginal Costs, stored energy value, water volume value
- **Economic:** operation, emission, and reliability costs and revenues from operation and operating reserves
- **Flexibility:** flexibility provided by demand, by the different generation and consumption technologies, and by power not served

Output files are specified at <https://opentepes.readthedocs.io/en/latest/OutputResults.html>. As an example see Figure 4 and Figure 5.

Figure 4: Map of network and relative flows

Figure 5: Generation by technologies

2.2.4 OpenTEPES additional documentation

- Model documentation
 - <https://opentepes.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>.
- Mathematical formulation:
 - <https://opentepes.readthedocs.io/en/latest/MathematicalFormulation.html>
- Input files specifications
 - <https://opentepes.readthedocs.io/en/latest/InputData.html>.
- Output files specifications
 - <https://opentepes.readthedocs.io/en/latest/OutputResults.html>

2.2.5 OpenTEPES References

- [7] Ramos, E. Quispe, S. Lumbreras “OpenTEPES: Open-source Transmission and Generation Expansion Planning” SoftwareX 18: June 2022 [10.1016/j.softx.2022.101070](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.softx.2022.101070)

2.3 plan4res

2.3.1 Scope of plan4res

plan4res is a power system model, which includes capacity expansion (adaptation of the generation and storage mix as well as of the existing interconnections of a given year), optimization of the strategies for managing seasonal storages, and simulation of the system operation.

Technologies: plan4res focuses on electricity. It includes all power generation technologies, electricity storage technologies, a (usually aggregated) representation of the interconnections between regions (the transmission grid within one region is not represented, nevertheless, the granularity of regions can be adapted to the modelling needs).

plan4res can run on any geographic scope, provided that it is divided into a set of interconnected regions and that data are available at regional granularity.

plan4res usually runs on a year, with hourly granularity.

Limitations may arise linked to the size of the problems to be solved.

2.3.2 Detailed description of plan4res

plan4res is an electricity system optimization and simulation tool, composed of the 3 following models:

- A Capacity expansion model (CEM) aimed at adapting the electricity mix
- A seasonal storage valuation model (SSV) aimed at optimizing the management of seasonal storages
- A simulation tool, based on a Unit Commitment model (UC), aimed at optimizing the short term operation of the system

Those 3 models cannot be described independently as:

- The Seasonal Storage Valuation Model itself uses the European Unit Commitment Model for solving its inner transition problem
- The Capacity Expansion Model uses the Unit Commitment model alone, or the Seasonal Storage Valuation Model (and the Unit Commitment model) for the evaluation of its operation cost function

This means that CEM cannot be ran without EUC, or SSV and UC, and SSV cannot be ran without UC, while UC can be ran alone, and SSV-UC can be ran without CEM.

All 3 models share the exact same set of data.

Capacity Expansion Model

The capacity expansion model is concerned with finding a (better) or ideally optimal set of assets including generation plants, interconnection capacities between clusters and distribution grid capacities, for the considered time horizon. Here optimal means, providing the least-cost set of assets, while accounting at best for the modelled constraints.

The objective is thus to design the optimal generation mix with the optimal transmission and distribution grid capacities for a given long-term horizon (e.g. 2050). The problem then consists in minimizing the sum of the annualized investment cost induced by installing new capacity in the electrical system and the expected operation cost of the system with the given installed capacity.

The model is also able to respect specific additional constraints (if wished by the user):

- Each region is able to produce the amount of energy required to meet the demand

- Or each region has to reach a target in terms of renewable generation energy share (including hydro)

Seasonal Storage Valuation Model

The Seasonal Storage Valuation Model solves a mid-term problem, where mid-term stands usually for annual. This problem consists in evaluating an approximation of the expected operation cost for a given installed capacity, under uncertainty.

Note that uncertainties (such as reservoir inflows, demand, outages or intermittent generation) are impacting operation decisions which are made dynamically along the mid-term horizon, while those uncertainties are progressively revealed and the forecasts are accordingly updated. Hence, the Seasonal Storage Valuation Model consists of a multi-stage stochastic optimization problem, aiming at minimizing the sum of operation costs on each stage of the horizon, accounting for non anticipativity constraints, as well as dynamical constraints (relating reservoir levels between two stages, ramping rates or any other conditions that involves linking adjacent time steps).

This problem is solved by time decomposition using stochastic dynamic programming. At each stage of the time horizon, a transition problem is solved, involving operational cost of the current stage and the cost-to go function giving the minimum future operational expected cost. The transition cost is evaluated by the Unit Commitment Model (see below).

Unit Commitment Model

The unit commitment problem solves the short-term horizon problem (short-term meaning daily or weekly), where operational decisions are taking into account the “value” that seasonal storage units can bring to the system via the cost-to-go function. The Unit Commitment Model is used in two ways.

- For solving the transition problem of the Seasonal Storage Valuation Model with a convexification of the operational constraints. Notice that the associated operational decisions may be infeasible since non-convex technical constraints have been convexified.
- For computing a feasible generation dispatch, without any convexification of technical constraints, accounting for the approximations of the cost-to-go functions provided by the Seasonal Storage valuation. In practice the model is used sequentially for each stage of the time horizon, and averaged over Monte Carlo simulations of the uncertainties.

Various kinds of flexibilities involving both generation, storage and consumption are modelled:

- Dynamic operation constraints of power plants (ramping constraints, minimum shut-down duration, ...)
- Dynamic operation of storage (including battery-like storages and complex hydro-valleys modelling)
- Demand-Response (including e.g. household dynamic consumption load-shifting or load curtailment)
- The model can also account for both transmission and distribution networks:
- Transmission Network representation: from a copper plate approach to a ‘clustered’ approach with limited transport capacities.
- Electricity distribution limited capacities and reinforcement costs

Figure 6: plan4res modelling suite

2.3.3 plan4res Inputs and Outputs

Inputs and outputs in plan4res are in either in csv or excel format.

Main Inputs:

- **Electricity demand:** hourly electricity demand or hourly profiles and annual electricity demand
- **System services requirements:** primary and secondary reserve (if relevant), Inertia requirements
- **Interconnections:** characteristics of (existing) transmission lines between regions: capacity, investment cost, impedance (if needed)
- **Generation mix:**
 - **Thermal generation** (fossil, nuclear, biomass plants): installed capacity, availability schedules and any other restriction, variable and capital costs, system services capacity, dynamic constraints if the user wishes to represent plants individually
 - **Hydro power**, including seasonal storage (reservoirs with large capacity, which are managed in general over one year), **(short term) storage:** this relates to small reservoirs, managed over 1 week or 1 day and run of river : installed capacity, volumes of reservoirs (if any), pumping efficiency, inflows, system services capacities, costs (for short term storage)
 - **Variable renewable generation (other than hydro), mainly windpower and PV:** installed capacity, system services capacities (if relevant), costs, hourly profiles which applied to the capacity give the hourly maximum power, depending on meteorological conditions (can be scenarized)
 - **(short term) storage** (apart from hydro): installed capacity, volume of the storage, charging / discharging efficiencies , inflows or independent demand (eg for EV -Electric Vehicle- storage), costs

Main Outputs:

- Investment decisions: generation, storage, interconnections
- Power generation schedules
- System services mobilisation schedules
- Inertia procurement schedules
- Volume of reservoirs
- Marginal costs of electricity
- Marginal costs of system services and of interconnections
- Flows between regions

2.3.4 plan4res additional documentation

- Mathematical formulation:
 - [Description – openenergymodels.net](https://openenergymodels.net)
- Documentation for installation and run of the model
 - <https://openenergymodels.net/models/plan4res-modelling-suite/install-plan4res/>
 - <https://openenergymodels.net/models/plan4res-modelling-suite/run-plan4res/>
- Data format
 - <https://openenergymodels.net/models/plan4res-modelling-suite/data-format-and-linkages/>

2.3.5 plan4res references

- [8] D. Beulertz, M. Franken, N. Oudjane, W. van Ackooij, J. Schweiger, I. Konstaltelos, P. Djapic, & D. Pudjianto. (2020). plan4res D3.1: Description of model interconnections (4.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3904272>
- [9] D. Beulertz, S. Charousset, D. Most, S. Giannelos and I. Yueksel-Erguen, "Development of a Modular Framework for Future Energy System Analysis," *2019 54th International Universities Power Engineering Conference (UPEC)*, Bucharest, Romania, 2019, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/UPEC.2019.8893472. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8893472>

2.4 InfraFair

2.4.1 Scope of InfraFair

The InfraFair model determines the network utilisation by agents (demand and generators using the network) and countries. Based on this utilisation and assuming that it reflects the economic benefits received by agents, it determines the responsibility of each agent in the construction of each element in the network. In order to reasonably reflect agent utilisation of infrastructure, multiple representative snapshots of the annual network usage should be provided. InfraFair is a decision support tool for network cost allocation and tariff design for regional power transmission infrastructure, but it can be used for national infrastructure as well as other types of infrastructures operating on the same principle of flow (e.g. gas and hydrogen). Hence, the model includes all assets that have a flow usage such as power lines, transformers, breaks, series capacitors and phase shifting transformers.

2.4.2 Detailed description of InfraFair

The model is aimed at computing the allocation of the cost of energy infrastructure according to the economic use of it expected to be made by agents. This should drive efficient investment decisions. The model employs the Average Participations Method (APM) to determine the usage of the network elements by agents. This allocates the network cost based on the electrical usage that each agent makes of each network asset as a reasonable proxy to the benefits, the former is obtaining from the latter. The basic intuition behind the APM is that the sources of the supply to loads and the destination of the power injected by generators, as well as the responsibility for causing the power flows, can be assigned by employing very simple heuristic flow tracing rules that only make use of the actual pattern of network flows.

The method requires as its basic input data a collection of snapshots of the network power flows corresponding to the specific system conditions of interest. The APM cost allocation algorithm assumes that electricity flows can be traced—or the responsibilities for causing them can be assigned— by supposing that at any network node, the inflows are distributed proportionally among the outflows. This is the so-called proportionality assumption. Implicit in this rule is the assumption that electricity does not flow in the opposite direction to that of the prevalent (net) flow over each line, which, according to this assumption, is the only existing flow (APM neglects the existence of counterflows). Based on these assumptions, the method traces the flow of electricity from individual sources to individual sinks. In other words, the model identifies, for each generator injecting power into the network, physical paths starting at this generator that go through the grid until they reach certain loads where they end. The method also works the other way around, thus identifying paths from loads to generators. Those paths coincide with the ones starting from generators. Therefore, the results of allocating the usage made of each element in the grid to generators and loads when applying APM one way and the other are the same. Besides, according to APM, the entire flow on each grid element originates in some generators and ends in some loads, which means that, according to this method, the overall usage made of this network element by loads is the same as that made by generators. Lastly, the cost of each network element is allocated to the different grid users according to how much power produced or consumed by each user flows on this network element. Figure 7 below depicts a schematic representation of a network featuring 4 transmission lines and 5 nodes. G1 and G2 are two nodes where two generators inject power into the grid. Nodes D1, D2 and D3 are three nodes where there is only power consumption.

Figure 7: Case example to illustrate application of proportionality in APM

Provided that all four transmission lines (L1, L2, L3, L4) can accommodate the power flows resulting from the unconstrained economic dispatch, the use of each transmission line is allocated in APM to generators and demands in the system according to the following. The participation of each agent in the flow through each line is obtained as that part of this flow that originates, or ends, in this agent, as shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Allocation of contract capacity to generators and demand with InfraFair

Use	Line 1	Line 2	Line3	Line4
G1 use	$[15 \times 20 / (40 + 20)] = 5 \text{ MW}$	$[35 \times 20 / (40 + 20)] = 11.7 \text{ MW}$	20 MW	Nothing
G2 use	$[15 \times 40 / (40 + 20)] = 10 \text{ MW}$	$[35 \times 40 / (40 + 20)] = 23.3 \text{ MW}$	Nothing	40 MW
TOTAL	15 MW	35 MW	20 MW	40 MW
D1 use	15 MW	Nothing	$[20 \times 15 / (10 + 15 + 35)] = 5 \text{ MW}$	$[40 \times 15 / (10 + 15 + 35)] = 10 \text{ MW}$
D2 use	Nothing	35 MW	$[20 \times 35 / (10 + 15 + 35)] = 11.7 \text{ MW}$	$[40 \times 35 / (10 + 15 + 35)] = 23.3 \text{ MW}$
D3 use	Nothing	Nothing	$[20 \times 10 / (10 + 15 + 35)] = 3.3 \text{ MW}$	$[40 \times 10 / (10 + 15 + 35)] = 6.7 \text{ MW}$
TOTAL	15 MW	35 MW	20 MW	40 MW

The final output of the model is the cost that each generator and demand should pay to recover the cost of each of the network asset. The cost that each country and each Transmission System Operator (TSO) should pay (per network asset) is then calculated by aggregating the costs of the generators and demand in their networks. In addition, the result includes the total cost that each country and each TSO should receive by aggregating the due costs of the assets in their networks.

In addition to the final cost allocation outputs, several intermediary results can be produced for each scenario. These include the contribution of agents, countries, or TSO areas to the flow and the utilization of the network assets, as well as the aggregate utilization factors of each agent, country, or TSO area of the assets of each type (within each group).

2.4.3 InfraFair Inputs and Outputs

Main Inputs:

- Nodal generation injections and withdrawals
- Flows
- Losses
- Length of lines
- Annual cost to be recovered for each line
- Capacity of lines
- Voltage of lines
- Are lines existing or planned? Regional or national?
- Names/IDs or owners of nodes and percentage of ownership

Main Outputs:

- Generation flow contribution: flow for each asset that each generator (or a group of generators) is causing (per snapshot and globally)
- Demand flow contribution: flow for each asset that each demand (or a group of demand) is causing (per snapshot and globally)
- Country flow contribution: flow for each asset that each country (generators and demand) is causing (per snapshot and globally)
- Agent usage: usage of each asset by each agent (per snapshot and globally)
- Agent usage fraction: fraction of each asset used by each agent (per snapshot and globally)
- Country usage fraction: fraction of each asset used by each country (per snapshot and global)
- Generation cost contribution: fraction of the cost of each asset that each generator (or a group of generators) is responsible for
- Generation cost contribution: fraction of the cost of each asset that each demand (or a group of demand) is responsible for
- Country cost contribution: fraction of the cost of each asset that each country (generators and demand) is responsible for
- Agent/Country cost: overall cost of the grid of each country that each agent/country is responsible for
- Agent/Country network cost: overall network cost that each agent/country is responsible for
- Country received cost: overall cost of the grid of each country that external agents from each other country are responsible for

2.4.4 InfraFair additional documentation

- Model documentation
 - <https://infrafair.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>
- Download repository
 - <https://github.com/IIT-EnergySystemModels/InfraFair>

2.4.5 InfraFair references

- [10] Olmos, L., & Perez-Arriaga, I. J. (2007). Evaluation of Three Methods Proposed for the Computation of Inter-TSO Payments in the Internal Electricity Market of the European Union. *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, 22(4), 1507–1522. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRS.2007.907118>

2.5 OnSSET

2.5.1 Scope of OnSSET

OnSSET is a Geographic Information Systems (GIS) based tool that enhances electrification planning and decision-making for the accomplishment of energy access goals in currently unserved areas. The OnSSET code base is modular and allows the users to specify spatial and temporal resolution of the analysis, GIS input data, technologies and costs. OnSSET is a bottom-up medium- to long-term optimization model that attempts to determine the least-expensive supply alternative to achieve universal electrification in each site by combining population settlements with various geographical features, socioeconomic data, and demographic information.

2.5.2 Detailed description of OnSSET

The OnSSET Geospatial Electrification Model focuses on investigating the least cost solution to the problem of guaranteeing access to electricity to every user in a certain area, identified by means of (GIS), with deployment of different solutions, usually (i) Grid Expansion, (ii) Minigrids or (iii) Stand-Alone Systems. The optimization is constrained by geo-morphological characterization of the area and techno-economical parameters for every technology exogenously provided to the model. The most suitable technology is identified per each of the clusters in which the study area is divided. The logical framework of the adopted model is reported in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Framework of the Open Source Spatial Electrification Toolkit (OnSSET). Adapted from: (Mentis et al., 2017)

The methodology assessed for the GIS-based investigation of the least cost electrification strategy is described in the following, step by step.

Population Clusterization and Electric Demand Estimation

Once identified, the study area is divided in clusters based on population aggregations; in such way, all human settlements are treated independently and georeferenced. The clusters, or human settlements, with no access to electricity are then identified based on analysis of satellite night-time lights and power distribution grid morphology. Per every unelectrified cluster, the number of households is computed based on population census; also, a target for electricity demand to be satisfied is set for each household, based on the multi-tier framework from the World Bank.

Resource Availability Estimation

Once the electricity demand is computed for each of the clusters, the evaluation of the resource availability is carried out, in order to estimate the Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCoE) of the seven investigated supply technologies. In this phase, the solar potential, the wind availability and the small and mini hydro potential of each cluster are estimated. Alongside with this, diesel cost information, existing and planned road network maps, existing and planned transmission and distribution network and morphology of the country (in terms of land use and terrain elevation) are collected. This second set of parameters helps investigating i) the incremental price of diesel, depending on the distance of the settlement from main roads and markets, ii) the distance from the existing and planned distribution grid, and iii) the natural boundaries to be respected when planning grid network expansion.

Off-Grid Supply Technologies Cost Comparison

In the third step, based on the data collected in the previous steps, six technologies are compared, as well as solution for granting access to electricity to the identified settlements:

- Stand-Alone PV
- Stand-Alone Diesel Generator
- Hydro Minigrid
- Solar Minigrid
- Wind Minigrid
- Diesel Minigrid

The technology able to provide the lower LCoE per each cluster is assigned as preferred solution for the element.

Grid Expansion Cost Evaluation

Once the optimal off-grid solution is identified for each cluster, a seventh option is added to the mix: the LCoE of the “expansion of the grid” solution is computed per every cluster. In clusters where grid extension cost is lower, the optimal solution is substituted with “Grid”, and the necessary lines registered as “planned”. The analysis is then performed again, accounting for the new “planned MV -Medium Voltage- lines”. In case this second round identifies new clusters suitable for grid expansion, the preference is updated and the loop continues; otherwise, the analysis stops and every cluster has an optimal technological solution assigned.

2.5.3 OnSSET Inputs and Outputs

OnSSET is a GIS-based tool and therefore requires data in a geographical format. In the context of the power sector, necessary data includes those on current and planned infrastructure (electric grid networks, road networks, power plants, industry, public facilities), population characteristics (distribution, location), and local renewable energy flows.

Main Inputs:

- Population:
 - Population size (now and projected)
 - Population distribution
 - Ratio of urban population in the selected area in the base year and in the end year

- Number of people per household in rural/urban areas
- Administrative boundaries
- Power Grid:
 - Existing HV -High Voltage- network (Optional) : Used to identify and spatially calibrate the currently electrified/non-electrified population.
 - Power Substations (Optional): used to calibrate the currently electrified/non-electrified population and specify grid extension suitability.
 - Planned High Voltage network (including extension to current/future substations, power plants, mines and queries). (Optional)
 - Existing and planned Medium Voltage network (Optional): Used to identify and spatially calibrate the currently electrified/non-electrified population.
 - Grid losses
 - Maximum distance for which the grid can be extended in order to electrify a settlement due to techno-economic considerations. The default value in the model is 50 km.
 - Maximum distance from the existing or planned grid network under which the model will consider a settlement as electrified
 - Maximum distance from the existing or planned road network under which the model will consider a settlement as electrified
- Roads and travel:
 - Current Road infrastructure used to identify and spatially calibrate the currently electrified/non-electrified population. It is also used in order to specify grid extension suitability. (Optional)
 - Travel time: Visualizes spatially the travel time required to reach from any individual cell to the closest town with population more than 50,000 people.
- Electricity demand:
 - Custom electricity demand in the end year in each settlement (Optional).
 - Annual electricity consumption per household that is expected to be achieved, by the end year
 - Ratio between the base and peak load in the selected country
- Nighttime lights: used to identify and spatially calibrate the currently electrified/non-electrified population.
- Global Horizontal Irradiation (used to identify availability/suitability of photovoltaic systems):
- Wind speed: used to identify the availability/suitability of wind power (using Capacity factors).
- Hydro power potential (Optional): mini/small hydropower potential, incl. environmental, social and topological restrictions
- Elevation Map
- Land Cover
- Service transformers (Optional): used to identify and spatially calibrate the currently electrified/non-electrified population.
- Costs and prices:
 - Capital costs per technologies: stand-alone diesel generator, stand-alone PV module, mini-grid diesel generator, mini-grid PV system, mini-grid wind powered system, mini grid hydropower system
 - Incremental cost increase for extension of the grid from an electrified settlement to an un-electrified one. Default value set at 10%.
 - Discount rate applied to different technology configuration choices throughout the period of analysis
 - Diesel price (low/high)
 - Grid Price, i.e., cost of generating electricity based on the technologies mix
 - Capital cost of additional grid capacity investment
 - Incremental cost increase for extension of the grid from an electrified settlement to an un-electrified one

- Electrification rate in the selected area in the base year: What ratio of population is electrified
- Minimum population value under which the model will consider a settlement as electrified

Main Outputs:

- Population served by each technology in the end year Sectoral Demands
- Number of newly electrified population by each technology in the end year
- Additional capacity required by each technology to fully cover the demand in the end year
- Investment required by each technology to reach the electrification target in the end year
- Generation mix as calculated by the OnSSET analysis
- Lowest LCoE achieved in each location as calculated by the OnSSET analysis

2.5.4 OnSSET additional documentation

<https://onsset.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>

<https://onsset.readthedocs.io/en/latest/references.html>

2.5.5 OnSSET references

- [11] Mentis, D., Howells, M., Rogner, H., Korkovelos, A., Arderne, C., Zepeda, E., Siyal, S.H., Taliotis, C., Bazilian, M., De Roo, A., Tanvez, Y., Oudalov, A., Scholtz, E., 2017. Lighting the World, The first global application of an open source, spatial electrification tool (OnSSET), with a focus on Sub-Saharan Africa. Environmental Research Letters Special Focus on Energy Access for Sustainable Development

2.6 EV-PV

2.6.1 Scope of EV-PV

The main goal of EV-PV is to support planning and decision-making for the deployment of charging stations for electric vehicles (EVs). The EV-PV model is a set of geospatial data layers and calculation modules implemented in the open source *Citiwatts* platform (<https://citiwatts.net/>). This tool, developed as part of the ERANET OpenGIS4ET project, is a GIS (Geographic Information System) tool for territorial energy planning. It is based on the previously developed *Hotmaps* platform. Technological scope: for the time being, the EV-PV model focuses on passenger cars, as this is the main mode of road passenger transport in Europe.

Geographic scope: the model can be applied to any geographic area, provided the data is available. The resolution of geospatial layers can go down to the hectare level.

Temporal scope: the model mainly focuses on values defined on a daily basis.

About the EV-PV model in the African context

The EV-PV model is expected to evolve quite significantly based on the available data and the specific needs of the African context. Whether in terms of scope, methodology or inputs/outputs, further investigation and model development is required before arriving at the final model description. Therefore, we only provide a very general description here.

2.6.2 Detailed description of EV-PV

Here, we briefly describe the three key features covered by the EV-PV model: 1) Assessment of the geospatial EV charging demand for passenger transport; 2) Identifying the optimal deployment of charging stations to meet the demand; 3) Assessment of the potential benefits and opportunities offered by PV coupling. It should be noted that EV-PV also aims to quantify the impact of EV on the electric grid and the energy dispatch. However, these features are still under development, and are therefore not described.

First, the model allows to calculate the geospatial distribution of charging needs in a user-selected region of interest. A typical map of the charging needs obtained with the EV-PV model is shown in Figure 9. The calculation of the demand is mainly based on population data, mobility habits and technical data of passenger cars (see section 2.6.3). These can be automatically set based on the data available for the selected region or customized by the user to perform "what-if" analysis.

Figure 9: Daily charging demand map calculated for the city of Milano. The area selected for the study is shown in blue

Second, once the charging needs are known, the optimal geographical deployment of charging stations is assessed. The primary output is the density of charging stations to cover the demand based on different charging scenarios: at home, at work, or at various points of interest (POIs). At this stage, potential coupling with PV can be evaluated to identify new pathways and opportunities to meet the charging needs. Nevertheless, at now this feature is still being developed, even for Europe: it covers potential coupling with residential PV in a PV-to-vehicle scheme while other coupling scheme are under development (grid, vehicle-to-X).

2.6.3 EV-PV Inputs and Outputs

Figure 10 depicts a simplified version of the inputs and outputs of the EV-PV model. For the interested reader, a more detailed list of the current EV-PV model inputs/outputs used in the European context (a priori, not necessarily relevant for Africa) has been provided in Task 3.1.

Figure 10: Simplified schematic of the inputs and outputs of the EV-PV model

As already stated, calculating the demand for electric charging requires input data on three key dimensions: population, mobility habits, and technical characteristics of the vehicle fleet. The accuracy of the final result is highly dependent on the quality of this data, which should ideally be available in layered form in order to adapt

to the local context. In particular, having population data with a high spatial resolution is an important condition for accurate modelling.

Output data mainly consists of layers showing the geospatial distribution of the EV charging demand and the potential locations for charging stations. To calculate the latter, it should be noted that the EV-PV model also requires: 1) “standard” geospatial data (such as road infrastructure and location of POIs), which is generally preprocessed; 2) data on local PV potential and/or production in order to evaluate PV coupling.

While all this input data is generally available in Europe, it is more difficult to obtain in many African countries. One should also note that the African context is different from that of Europe. In particular, it is well known that there is a wider variety of modes of passenger transport to consider (private car is often not the main mode), which calls for considering a broader technological scope. This is also important to consider the great differences between countries regarding passenger transport (for instance, the vehicle fleet and the mobility habits). As for coupling with PV, standalone systems or mini-grids are also important systems to consider. Available data on all these aspects must be collected to converge towards a more detailed set of inputs and outputs tailored to the African context.

2.6.4 EV-PV references

[12] Citiwatts, online platform hosted by HES-SO: <https://citiwatts.net/>

[13] Jeannin, Noémie and Pena-Bello, Alejandro and Ballif, Christophe and Wyrsh, Nicolas, Mapping the Charging Demand for Electric Vehicles in 2050 from Mobility Habits. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4604192>

2.7 Plexos

2.7.1 Scope of Plexos

PLEXOS Integrated Energy Model is a simulation software designed for energy market analysis. It was first developed as an electricity market simulator. Its functionality was then extended so that the recent versions of PLEXOS integrate electric power, gas, heat and water. PLEXOS is a high-performance simulation platform, operationally used by energy market participants, system planners, investors, regulators, consultants and analysts worldwide. The PLEXOS simulations are based on mathematical programming. The system supports various planning horizons from long-term to short-term, and several different time steps: the simulated time frames can range from minutes and hours to tens of years. The PLEXOS models can capture specifics of short-term operational limits, as well as the effects of system expansion.

2.7.2 Model Description

The PLEXOS model considers more detailed operational characteristics and performance of the system and has been used worldwide for many system expansion and renewable integration studies. For example, the PLEXOS model simultaneously analyzes and optimizes the generation and transmission systems, with N-1 contingency analysis; co-optimizes energy and reserve provision on an hourly time scale; models detailed characteristics of generating units such as ramp rates, minimum up and down time, minimum energy provision, hydrological constraints (e.g., reservoir, cascades) and uses unit start costs for unit commitment decisions.

Product simulation uses security constrained unit commitment and dispatch with N-1 contingency analysis and simultaneous co-optimization of energy and reserves. Production simulation is the key part of the operational analysis, used to estimate overall system performance, and renewable integration impacts.

The PLEXOS model evaluates new resource additions by looking at the planning horizon and adding new generation projects to minimize total system costs, taking into account all input and system constraints. New generation addition decisions are based on economics. Production simulation and optimization programs build the least-cost plan by adding new generating resources when they are economical, that is when their benefits exceed their costs, including their investment costs. During this process, the model evaluates many combinations of available resource additions and selects the set, the units, and schedule that produce the lowest discounted cost over the study horizon. PLEXOS output results show the least-cost expansion plan with near-optimal alternatives.

2.7.3 PLEXOS Input and Output Variables

PLEXOS simulates the fundamental principle of operation of the electricity market, also known as "market clearing" while minimizing system costs for each hour of the selected forecasting period. Mathematical calculation algorithms – deterministic or stochastic – are used depending on the forecast period and the accuracy of model inputs (technical constraints, weather profiles, commodity prices, etc.). Typically, deterministic methods are used for short-term periods (up to 1–6 months), where the assumption of "perfect foresight" for inputs is accepted. Stochastic methods are used for longer-term predictions, where it is necessary to assess the volatility of inputs, i.e. for volatile variables, a sample of variable parameters ($N, N_1, \dots, N_{x-1}, N_x$, where N is the annual profile of a specific parameter) are used, allowing assessment of edge cases as well.

Figure 11: Plexos model design

The scope of model and data inputs is massive, ranging from technical parameters of specific generation unit to the economic indicators of commodities. The accuracy of model outputs also depends on the granularity of the data (annual, monthly, or hourly data). The biggest challenge is to manage the flow of data and identify scenarios that are relevant to the topic.

2.7.4 PLEXOS case study – Ethiopia

PLEXOS model has been used in Ethiopia to update the earlier Master Plan Study focusing on the generation expansion plan for the horizon years of from 2019-2030. In employing the PLEXOS model, the study uses industry state of the art tools and methodologies to model power system operations and economics, develop reserve requirements based on load and intermittent resource variability, model wind and solar resource economics, and develop system performance indicators that are used to evaluate the value of system resources for energy provision, reserve provision, and for flexibility.

2.7.5 PLEXOS references

[14] <https://openenergy-platform.org/factsheets/models/152/>

[15] Grid Management Support Program System Integration Study (GMSP-SIS), Power Africa.

[16] <https://ignitinnovation.com/plexos-smart-way-of-doing-things/>

2.8 SPLAT-Africa

2.8.1 Scope of SPLAT-Africa

System Planning Test (SPLAT) Africa is a long-term capacity expansion model that includes the five SPLAT models of the African regions (North, East, West, South and Center). Most recently, the SPLAT-MESSAGE framework has been endorsed as the official planning tool for the development of the African Continental Power Systems Master Plan (CMP), an initiative led by the African Union Development Agency (AUDA) with the technical and financial support of the European Union (EU).

2.8.2 Detailed description of SPLAT-Africa

The model consists of a database, an Excel-based interface and an optimization model. The database is IRENA's own database of national power systems that covers a detailed representation of power system capacity expansion in 47 African countries. The optimization model used is MESSAGE software, developed by IIASA (MESSAGE is free for use for academic purposes only). The Excel interface is used to feed inputs to MESSAGE and extract output from it.

The IRENA SPLAT models are uniquely calibrated to represent national supply structures and regional interconnections, and they allow national energy planners to assess a wide range of least-cost supply scenarios. These models are built on IRENA's state-of-the-art knowledge of renewable technologies featured in various databases and analyses, including cost data, resource potentials and renewable zones. These were recently augmented with the newly developed African Renewable Electricity Profiles (AfREP) for Energy Modelling Databases on Hydropower, Solar PV and wind (what is also known as Model Supply Regions).

2.8.3 SPLAT-Africa Inputs and Outputs

The model inputs consist of an exhaustive list of existing and planned technologies and their costs per country, which includes:

- Demand
- Transmission
- Distribution
- Fuel Prices
- Generic Technologies
- Generic Technologies costs
- Specific Technologies
- Specific Technologies costs
- Battery Storage
- PV Zones
- Wind Zones
- CSP (Concentrated Solar Power) zones
- Interconnectors

The model outputs consist of an exhaustive list of capacity expansion for the various technologies (generation and transmission) per country, which includes:

- Capacity
- New capacity
- Renewable capacity
- CO2 emission
- Costs
- Generation profile

2.8.4 SPLAT-Africa references

[17] SPLAT Dashboard: Africa Results.

https://public.tableau.com/views/IRENA_SPLAT_Africa/MainDashboard?:showVizHome=no&:embed=yes

[18] Africa Power Sector: Planning and Prospects for Renewable Energy (synthesis report):

<https://www.irena.org/Publications/2015/Mar/Africa-Power-Sector-Planning-and-Prospects-for-Renewable-Energy-synthesis-report>

- [19] Southern African Power Pool: Planning and Prospects for Renewable Energy.
<https://www.irena.org/Publications/2013/Jun/Southern-African-Power-Pool-Planning-and-Prospects-for-Renewable-Energy>
- [20] West African Power Pool: Planning and Prospects for Renewable Energy.
<https://www.irena.org/Publications/2013/Jun/West-African-Power-Pool-Planning-and-Prospects-for-Renewable-Energy>
- [21] Planning and prospects for renewable power: West Africa.
<https://www.irena.org/Publications/2018/Nov/Planning-and-prospects-for-renewable-power>
- [22] Planning and prospects for renewable power: Eastern and Southern Africa.
<https://www.irena.org/Publications/2021/Apr/Planning-and-prospects-for-renewable-power-Eastern-and-Southern-Africa>
- [23] Planning and prospects for renewable power: North Africa.
<https://www.irena.org/Publications/2023/Jan/Planning-and-prospects-for-renewable-power-North-Africa>

2.9 Balmorel model

2.9.1 Scope of Balmorel

Balmorel is an open source economic and technical partial equilibrium model for analysing the electricity and combined heat and power sectors in an international perspective. It is highly versatile and may be applied for long range planning as well as shorter time operational analysis. It simulates the power system and least-cost dispatch, as well as optimizes investments in generation and dispatch. The model optimises production at the existing and planned production units and simultaneously simulates least-costs investments in new generation and transmission, thereby finding the regional least-cost way to supply the needed electricity. The investment projects (as well as the year of investment, location and capacity) are chosen by the model via an impartial and objective least-cost optimization approach based on the input data provided.

2.9.2 Detailed description of Balmorel

Balmorel is implemented as a mainly linear programming optimization problem. The model is developed and coded in GAMS model language, and the source code is readily available under open-source conditions, thus providing complete documentation of the functionalities. Moreover, the user may modify the model according to specific requirements, making the model suited for any purpose within the focus parts of the energy system.

Input data and calculation results are given in relation to a geographical subdivision that allows identification of countries (for description of e.g. taxes, emissions, etc.), regions (for electricity transmission) and areas (for district heating systems, local cost elements, etc.). Time aspects are treated flexibly in relation to how many years to represent, and how many subdivisions of the time within the year. Typical choices are 250 time segments per year over a 20 year time-horizon, or 8,760 time segments per year over one year, according to the purpose of the study. BALMOREL can simulate the electricity sector and some of the heat sector (district heating), but not the transport sector (transport technologies are not represented as standard, but some projects have developed transport sector modules). Technical and economic characteristics are given for an arbitrary number of production units, e.g. capacities, fuel efficiencies, operation and maintenance costs, fuel prices. The different types of units include electricity, heat, combined heat and power, short-term heat storages, hydro power, wind and solar. Specialties like electricity storage are provided to represent e.g. hydrogen storage or pumped hydro. Electricity transmission is described in relation to a number of nodes that are connected by transmission lines characterised by capacity, loss and cost. This flow model allows for the identification of bottlenecks in the transmission system, and thereby can show differences in electricity prices according to geography. In relation to generation capacity, the model may invest optimally in electricity and combined heat and power technologies. The investments respect specified restrictions e.g. in relation to maximum investment addition per year, or maximum fuel available. The model also handles environmental and other taxes, subsidies and quotas. Due to the model being formulated in a modelling system additional functionalities may be (and have been) developed as needed in relation to specific project needs, as indicated in some of the references below.

The BALMOREL model has been applied to projects in Denmark, Norway, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Germany, as well as in countries outside of Europe including for East African Power Pool (EAPP). It has been used for analyses of security of electricity supply, the role of demand response, wind power development, the role of natural gas, development of international electricity markets, market power, expansion of electricity transmission, international markets for green certificates and emission trading as well as environmental policy evaluation, unit commitment, CAES (Compressed Air Energy Storage) technology and learning curves. To date the BALMOREL has not simulated a 100% renewable-energy electricity sector or a 100% renewable-energy system: the highest renewable-penetrations simulated to date are 50% of the electricity sector, and 10% of the transport sector.

2.9.3 Balmorel Input and Output Variables

The model permits specification of geographically distinct entities. The main types of geographical entities are Areas, Regions, and Countries. Here are some examples of how entities are related to geographical level. The following entities are related to countries:

- environmental policy
- availability of certain fuels

The following entities are related to regions.

Related to electricity demand:

- annual nominal electricity demand
- variation within the year of the nominal electricity demand
- deviation from nominal electricity demand
- consumer price base for electricity
- variation within the year of the consumer price base for electricity

Related to electricity transmission and distribution:

- losses in electrical distribution
- cost of electrical distribution
- cost of electrical transmission
- losses in electrical transmission
- electricity export to third countries
- variation within the year of the electricity export to third countries
- initial capacity on electrical transmission
- investment cost for new electrical transmission capacity

Related to energy and fuels:

- availability of certain fuels

The following entities are related to areas:

Related to heat demand:

- annual nominal heat consumption
- variation within the year of the nominal heat demand
- deviation from nominal heat demand
- price base for heat
- variation within the year of the consumer price base for heat

Related to heat distribution:

- losses in heat distribution
- cost of heat distribution

Related to technologies:

- operation and maintenance cost for technologies
- capacity reduction factor for technologies
- efficiency reduction factor for technologies
- initial capacities of generation technologies
- investment cost for new technology

Related to fuels:

- fuel price

- availability of certain fuels
- annual quantity and variation between the seasons of water availability for dispatchable hydro generation
- annual quantity and variation within the year of non-dispatchable hydro generation
- annual quantity and variation within the year of wind power generation
- annual quantity and variation within the year of solar voltaic generation

2.9.4 Balmorel application to EAPP

Balmorel has been applied to study the EAPP Master plan by analysing the benefit of regional cooperation and to recommend a package of new cross-border transmission lines. The analysis includes 12 countries (i.e. Burundi, Djibouti, DRC, Egypt, Ethiopia, Kenya, Rwanda, Sudan, Tanzania, Uganda, South Sudan and Libya) in one model. The model includes a large area and long-time horizon, from 2015 to 2040 in five-year time steps.

21 scenarios are analysed including a main scenario and 20 alternative scenarios which vary a single parameter. This gives a detailed insight in the interactions and dynamics in the regional electricity system. Examples of parameters varied are: Electricity demand, fuel prices, delay of projects, interest rate, cost of transmission and generation, CO₂ price and targets for the share of renewable energy. The scenarios are used to analyse the robustness of different investments. This is important because of the uncertainty regarding the future development of many important parameters. In many studies investment in generation and transmission is analysed separately, e.g. what transmission is needed given a certain portfolio of generation. In the study, the model is investing simultaneously in generation and transmission. All scenarios find optimal solutions, and when a parameter is changed, the optimal investment in both generation and transmission will change.

Only secure investments in plants and transmission lines have been included as “existing” and “committed”. This gives more flexibility to the model to identify least-cost investments. Predictably, this (together with the regional as opposed to national focus of the study), may result in different regional power system planning projections compared to the ones prescribed in the national Master plans of the individual countries.

2.9.5 Balmorel references

[24] <http://www.balmorel.com/>

[25] https://www.ea-energianalyse.dk/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/1332_eapp_master_plan_2014_executive_summary.pdf

[26] <https://www.energyplan.eu/othertools/global/balmorel/>

[27] <https://wiki.openmod-initiative.org/wiki/Balmorel>

2.10 Antares

2.10.1 Scope of Antares

Antares-Simulator is an Open Source power system simulator meant to be used by anybody placing value in quantifying the adequacy or the economic performance of interconnected energy systems, at short or remote time horizons. With an adequate modelling of the energy consumption, generation and transportation, the software performs probabilistic simulations of the system throughout many year-long scenarios made of 8760 hourly time-frames each.

The Antares-Simulator project was initiated by RTE (French Electricity Transmission system Operator) in 2007.

The software is used to:

- Explore prospective visions of the energy sector
- Analyse the costs and benefits of a new generation or interconnection project
- Assess the impact of a given energy policy on the generation mix
- Evaluate the level of security of supply of the upcoming years

2.10.2 Model description of Antares

Antares simulates the economic behaviour of the whole transmission-generation system, throughout the year and with a resolution of one hour.

The power system is represented with a graph involving up to a few hundreds of country-sized or region-sized nodes, tied together by edges whose characteristics summarize those of the underlying power grid. Each node includes a description of its electrical demand, its reserve needs and its generation fleet, this last being composed of thermal units, hydro units (run-of-river units and seasonal reservoirs), intermittent renewable generation, pumping stations and storages.

Power flows are either ruled by Net Transfer Capacities (NTC) or by a conventional DC approximation with data in form of power transfer distribution factors (PTDF) or impedances. In both cases, additional binding constraints between flows can represent specific market rules (such as flow-based market coupling) and/or physical components (such as phase-shifting devices, DC lines).

For each considered scenario, Antares optimizes the unit-commitment and dispatch so as to meet the demand at the lowest cost. Each year is seen as a succession of weekly optimization sub-problems whose objective is the minimization of the electricity supply costs. All of these problems are defined at the spatial scale of the whole interconnected system. The kernel of the software is a linear solver developed by RTE which computes operating set-points for the whole system (optimal weekly unit-commitment, hydro-thermal scheduling and interconnection flows with an hourly resolution).

So as to deal conveniently with some difficult aspects of hydro-thermal optimal unit-commitment and dispatch (presence of both integer and real variables), simulation settings allow different formulations of the optimization problem with several trade-offs between computation time and accuracy. The most exhaustive simulation mode includes explicitly in the optimization problem the unit-commitment variables and the constraints and costs related to the flexibility of the generation units (minimum stable power, minimum up and down durations, start-up costs, no-load heat costs), while fastest modes solve a simplified (yet accurate enough for most uses) version of this problem within very short times.

2.10.3 Antares Inputs and Outputs

Figure 12: Overview of the Antares model workflow (source: antares-simulator.org)

Five inputs can be described as random variables in Antares: Availability of thermal power plants, load, wind power generation, solar generation and hydraulic inflows.

They are represented in the software with several time-series, each one being a possible realisation of the variable for the studied future horizon.

Simulation results involve all of the variables related to the system operation (unit-commitment and generation level for each unit, flow through each tie-line), hour by hour and for all scenarios. Results such as loss of load duration, unsupplied energy or generation margins give an assessment of the security of supply in the different zones of the simulated system. In addition, the tool gives an account of the CO₂ emissions, as well as an assessment of the economic performance of the whole system (various estimates such as operation costs, locational marginal prices, congestion fees, etc.).

Simulation results can be written with several time resolution (hourly to annual) and spatial resolution (one link, one area, one set of areas). Antares also gives the possibility to analyse the simulation results through probabilistic indicators (expected value averaged over all scenarios, standard deviation, minimum and maximum, etc.) and through the detailed realisation of each variable for all considered scenarios. Filtering options in the software enables to select which output to write in a given study.

2.10.4 Antares references

[28] <https://antares-simulator.org/>.

2.11 PSS-E

2.11.1 Scope of PSS-E

PSS-E (Power System Simulator for Engineering) is an electrical system simulation software owned by Siemens.

It is used for static studies (distribution of power flows, network losses, calculation of short-circuit currents) and also for dynamic studies (simulate the behavior of an electrical system following one or more events, like the connection or disconnection of a structure, the triggering of a production group, the appearance and disappearance of a short circuit, a variation in voltage or power setpoint for a group, etc.)

2.11.2 Detailed description of PSS-E

The LoadFlow module (or load distribution module) is used for N distribution calculations (normal operating situation with all structures in service). This module makes it possible, thanks to a convergence algorithm, to determine the network voltage plan and the active and reactive power flows on all the structures of an electrical system. This distribution directly results in a certain amount of technical information such as the distribution of power flows and the total network losses.

To carry out these LoadFlow calculations, it is necessary to know the topology, the electrical characteristics of the transport and production structures, the dispatch (distribution of the load and the means of production in active power and in reactive power or voltage setpoint), the voltage instructions for transformers with an on-load tap changer or the taps used for transformers with an off-load tap changer.

A contingency analysis module ("AC contingency solution") is used for calculations in N-1 (operating situation with a structure unavailable). This module is based on an automated calculation of LoadFlow by disconnecting (in the case of N-1 analysis) a structure at each simulation.

A short-circuit current calculation module makes it possible in particular to calculate the intensity of single- and three-phase short circuits at each node of the network studied.

A dynamic simulation module makes it possible to simulate the behavior of an electrical system following one or more events occurring in a determined initial situation. This initial situation is defined during a power distribution or Load Flow calculation, the result of which is used as input data for the dynamic simulation. This initial situation - stable by definition before the occurrence of a dynamic event - makes it possible in particular to define the state variables of the systems or blocks of the dynamic network model. The events can be the connection or disconnection of a work, the triggering of a production group, the appearance and disappearance of a short circuit, a variation in voltage or power setpoint for a group, etc.

2.11.3 PSS-E Inputs and Outputs

A .sav file contains all the static information of the network to study. A .sld file for "single line diagram" contains its graphical representation.

For N-1 calculations, all of the structures to be disconnected are defined using .sub and .con files (definition of the structures to be triggered, specified by type of equipment and by subsystem(s)), and the criteria in a .mon file. The .con file contains the results of the N-1 calculation, in particular the load of the structures and the min and max tensions of the nodes which are outside the criteria provided (in the .mon file).

For dynamic simulations, each object having a direct influence on the dynamics of the electrical system is associated under PSS-E with a model contained in an internal library. It is then up to the user to configure the model instance. The models in the library are essentially referenced models (models of loads, synchronous machines, asynchronous machines, etc.). Dynamic system information is contained in a .dyr file.

2.11.4 PSS-E References

[29] <https://www.siemens.com/global/en/products/energy/grid-software/planning/pss-software/pss-e.html>

3 Databases

3.1 World Databases

3.1.1 IRENA

IRENA statistics

IRENA publishes detailed statistics on renewable energy capacity, power generation and renewable energy balances. This data is collected directly from members using the IRENA Renewable Energy Statistics questionnaire and is also supplemented by desk research where official statistics are not available. Renewable power-generation capacity statistics are released every year in March. Additionally, renewable power generation and renewable energy balances datasets are released every year in July.

In particular this database includes:

- Public investment by country/area, technology (on and off-grid PV, solar thermal energy, concentrated solar power, onshore and offshore wind power, hydropower, marine energy, renewable and non-renewable municipal waste, liquid biofuels, biogas, other primary solid biofuels, geothermal energy, coal and peat, oil, natural gas, nuclear) and year (from 2000 to 2021)
- Heat generation (commercial heat and combined heat and power) by country/area, technology (solar thermal energy, renewable and non-renewable municipal waste, solid biofuels, biogas, geothermal energy, coal and peat, oil, natural gas, nuclear, fossil fuels, other non-renewable and renewable) and year (from 2000 to 2021)
- On-grid and Off-grid installed electricity capacity by country/area, technology (solar PV, solar thermal energy, onshore and offshore wind power, hydropower, marine energy, renewable municipal waste, solid and liquid biofuels, biogas geothermal energy, coal and peat, oil, natural gas, nuclear) and year (from 2000 to 2022)
- On-grid and Off-grid electricity generation by country/area, technology (solar PV, solar thermal energy, onshore and offshore wind power, hydropower, marine energy, renewable municipal waste, solid and liquid biofuels, biogas geothermal energy, coal and peat, oil, natural gas, nuclear) and year (from 2000 to 2022)

Source: <https://www.irena.org/Statistics>

IRENA Model Supply Regions (MSRs)

This database contains model-ready, technology-based datasets for the potential of solar and on-shore wind across the African countries. Each input technology includes energy information (capacity factor and energy potential), cost characteristics (levelized cost) as well as locational coordinates. The database can be downloaded in a form of a shape file and excel/csv files.

Source: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-022-01786-5>

3.1.2 AR6 Scenario Explorer and Database hosted by IIASA

This database (hosted in a IIASA Scenario Explorer) presents an ensemble of quantitative, model-based pathways underpinning the Sixth Assessment Report (AR6) of Working Group III by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), entitled *Climate Change 2022: Mitigation of Climate Change*

<https://data.ece.iiasa.ac.at/ar6>

3.1.3 Global solar and wind atlases

The database include the primary potential of solar and wind energy (in terms of irradiance and wind speed) across the entire world. The database can be downloaded in a form of a raster and it can be selected for a specific region or country.

Source: <https://globalsolaratlas.info/map> and <https://globalwindatlas.info/en>

3.1.4 GridFinder database

The database includes the existing transmission and distribution networks of all countries in the world (each with voltage and locational information). The database is based on opensource information and can be downloaded in the form of shape files or image (.tif) files for any region or country.

Source: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-019-0347-4>

3.1.5 Global Roads Inventory Project (GRIP)

The database includes information about existing and future roads around the world. It consists of global and regional vector datasets in ESRI file geodatabase and shapefile format and global raster datasets of road density at a 5 arcminutes resolution (~8x8km).

Source: <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1748-9326/aabd42>

3.1.6 COPERNICUS

COPERNICUS Land Monitoring Service

The Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (CLMS) provides geospatial information on land cover and its changes, land use, vegetation state, water cycle and Earth's surface energy variables to a broad range of users in Europe and across the World in the field of environmental terrestrial applications.

CLMS is jointly implemented by the European Environment Agency and the European Commission DG Joint Research Centre (JRC) and has been operational since 2012.

CLMS consists of five main components:

- The **systematic monitoring of biophysical parameters** produces mainly a series of qualified bio-geophysical products on the status and evolution of the land surface. This is produced at a global scale every ten days with a mid spatial resolution and is complemented by a long term time series. The products are used to monitor vegetation, crops, water cycle, energy budget and terrestrial cryosphere variables.
- **Land cover and land use mapping** produces land cover classifications at various level of detail, both within a pan-European and global context. At the pan-European level, these are complemented by detailed layers on land cover characteristics, such as imperviousness, forests, grassland, water and wetness and small woody features. At global level, the land cover mapping follows the FAO's modular-hierarchical Land Cover Classification System.
- **Thematic hot-spot mapping** aims to provide tailored and more detailed information on specific areas of interest, known as hot-spots. Hotspots in the context of CLMS are prone to specific environmental challenges.
- **Imagery and reference data** provide satellite image mosaic in high and very high resolutions and reference datasets. This includes, on the one hand, satellite image mosaic from contributing missions covering the territory of Europe as well as Sentinel-2 image mosaic production at global level. On the other hand, it consists of reference datasets providing homogeneous pan-European coverage of some key geospatial themes, such as hydrography and elevation.

- **Ground motion.** In addition to the above-mentioned components, a new European Ground Motion activity has been launched. The activity measures ground displacements, including landslides and subsidence, as well as deformation of infrastructure.

3.2 West Africa Databases

3.2.1 Ecowrex Observatory for Renewable energy and Energy Efficiency

ECOWREX is a web platform providing reliable data and information on energy resources, infrastructure and potential policy resources at regional and national level to help policy makers, project developers and investors as well as other stakeholders for evidence-based decision making and planning.

ECOWREX aims to provide reliable, targeted, up-to-date and above all open-source information. It will contribute to the creation of a network of experts in the field of energy and encourage cooperation between key local and international stakeholders.

ECOWREX includes several sections that make it easier for users to find the desired information. These sections include country profiles, spatial data and human activity resources that help us define the deployment period for specific energy technologies.

Data in ECOWREX come from different sources, including ECOWAS reports, ECREE reports, Ministries of energy, of economy of Works and Housing, Governmental reports, ECREE database, Azimut reports, Utilities reports, papers from conferences...

ECOWREX also include GIS data, among which

- Population density
- Land cover
- Electricity demand for urban / rural areas, 2023 and 2030
- Identified settlements for off-grid, and mini grid and their density (2023, 2030)
- Electricity and gas grids (transmission and distribution)
- Other infrastructure - Roads, Railway, Airports, Ports • Protected areas – environmental, military, urban, other protected uses (tourism, mining, industry, etc.)
- Renewable energy resources: solar, wind, small hydro, biomass from biocrops, and the potential for electricity generation
- Average wind speed
- On-Grid power plants (conventional and renewable energy)
- Existing and planned RE&EE programs and project sites
- RE&EE Key Stakeholders (universities, companies, ministries including contact data)
- Access to energy: Population electrified and non-electrified
- Energy efficiency
- RE&EE events

ECOWREX includes a country dataset for Renewable energy sector in the 15 countries (see Figure 13)

Resources	Renewable	Transmission	Distribution	Consumer price		
	Conventional			Energy (electricity) demand		
Installed capacity	Renewable		Transmission	Transmission	Electrification	
	Conventional				Purchase price	
Energy produced	Renewable			Transmission	Transmission	Sell price
	Conventional					Transmission lines
	Renewable	Energy supply chains				
	Conventional	Total electricity transmitted				
					Losses	
					Electrification rate	
				Storage facilities		

Figure 13: Country profile data in Renewable energy sector

The following variables are included (among others):

- Installed Capacity (in Mini-Grid, On-Grid and Off-Grid), MW per technology
- Generation Capacity GWh per technology
- Final Energy Consumption per Capita,
- Generation from Renewables (Share),
- Access to Electricity: for the whole country, and for rural or urban areas , % total of population and % total of households,
- Number and energy savings of Efficient Electrical Appliances / Efficient buildings / Improved Cook Stoves Efficient Lighting / Energy Efficient Industries / Energy-Efficient Refrigerators / Efficient Air Conditioners/ Modern Cooking Fuel
- Non-Technical Losses, Transmission Losses, Distribution Losses
-

Additionally, for each country, the platform includes Policies and regulatory framework, Socio-economic indicators and general data.

Ecowrex platform : <http://www.ecowrex.org/>

Website of Ecreee: <http://www.ecreee.org/>

3.2.2 SIE-UEMOA

UEMOA is an extension of the West African Monetary Union (UMOA) and has the following missions and objectives:

1. the unification of national economic areas, to transform the Union into a promising and attractive market for investors;
2. the consolidation of the macroeconomic framework of the Member States, through the harmonization of their economic policies, in particular budgetary, as well as by the strengthening of their common currency.

The SIE-UEMOA should in particular make it possible to provide:

- Detailed energy balances in IEA format ideally over more than ten years;
- Energy indicators (sectoral and energy policy monitoring);
- Environmental and climatic indicators;
- Results of prospective analysis of energy demand.

This database contains energy statistics from 2010 to 2020 for the countries of UEMOA: Benin, Burkina Faso, Côte d'Ivoire, Guinea-Bissau, Mali, Niger, Senegal and Togo, namely:

- Production
- Imports and exports
- Transformation
- Final energy consumption per sector (chemistry, steel, cement, residential, tertiary...)

For each kind of energy:

- Coal and manufactured gas,
- Natural gas,
- Oil
- Renewable energy and biomass,
- Electricity and heat

Source: <http://sie.uemoa.int/>

3.3 East Africa Databases

3.3.1 The African Energy Information System (AEIS):

AEIS is a decision-making tool which is comprised of a continental energy database and other energy information and data visualisation tools. The AEIS was created by AFREC (AFRICan Energy Commission) in 2012 to coordinate Africa's energy data collection, validation and dissemination at national, regional and continental level. The system facilitates exchange of energy information amongst African Union Member States, Regional Economic Communities (RECs) and other key stakeholders.

It includes data from 2000 to 2021 for all countries, such as

- Energy balance (primary supply per fuels, transformations, losses, final consumption) per country and year
- Production and imports per fuel
- Biomass potential (forest and land areas, deforestation areas, woodfuel and charcoal production and consumption, for rural or urban areas)
- Hydro power plants with their capacity and height of dam

Source: <https://au-afrec.org/african-energy-information-system>

3.3.2 The African Energy Commission (AFREC)

The African Energy Commission (AFREC) is an organ of the African Union in charge of ensuring, coordinating and harmonizing development and integration of energy resources on the African continent. AFREC officially launched on February 17th, 2008 in Algiers at the end of a conference of African Energy Ministers in charge of Energy. AFREC mandated to "Design, create and set up an energy continental data base and facilitate rapid dissemination of information and exchange of information among Member States, as well as among the Regional Economic Communities (RECs) and Regional Power Pools (RPPs) around Africa".

This database includes among others the following data:

- Economy: GDP, inflation, unemployment per country and year
- Energy: primary energy production and consumption, energy intensity, energy imports,
- Land Use

Source: <https://au-afrec.org/>

3.3.3 East African Community Data Portal

The East African Community (EAC) is a regional intergovernmental organisation of seven Partner States, comprising Burundi, Democratic Republic of Congo, Kenya, Rwanda, South Sudan, Tanzania and Uganda, with its headquarters in Arusha, Tanzania. The EAC Data Finder Repository is a common workplace that will allow data users to easily explore, visualize and download large datasets. This repository will provide a one-stop interface to access EAC statistical data in the following Sectors: External Sector, Government Finance, Consumer Price Index, Monetary and Finance, National Accounts, Agriculture Food and Nutrition, Poverty and Migration Statistics.

Source: <https://eac.opendataforafrica.org>

3.3.4 EAPP

The goal of the East African Power Pool (EAPP) is to be a framework for pooling energy resources, promoting power exchanges between utilities in Eastern Africa in order to secure their respective power supply, provide mutual assistance in case of failure in their respective power systems and reduce power supply costs based on an integrated master plan and pre-established rules (Grid code). There are currently thirteen member countries of the Eastern Africa Power Pool who have signed the Inter-Governmental Memorandum Of Understanding (IGMOU).

Source: <https://eappool.org/>

3.3.5 Other fragmented sources of data:

- Member states- Master plan, national reports, energy outlooks
- Ministry of Energy for each country
- African specialised institutions
- International Energy Database Providers (IEA, EIA, WB, UN, OPEC, IAEA, USAID, etc.)